

**Prabhakar
Research Group**
*Manufacturing &
Mechanics*

WEAVING RESILIENCE: ENGINEERING DAMAGE-TOLERANT TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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ARCHITECTED TEXTILE COMPOSITES

Weaving non-traditional and spatially tuned weave architectures

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Hridyesh Tewani, Jackson Cyvas, Kennedy Perez, and Pavana Prabhakar, Arxi-textile Composites: Role of Weave Architecture on Mode-I Fracture Energy in Woven Composites, *Composites Part A*, 2025.

Feng, P Subramaniyan, Tewani, And Prabhakar, Physics-Constrained Neural Network for Design and Feature-based Optimization of Weave Architectures, *Composites Part A*, 2024.

Hridyesh Tewani, Vincent Scheerer, Madison Owens, Emilio Cumbajin, Camila De Leon, Md Hussain, David Wallace, Pavana Prabhakar, "Arxi-Textile Composites II: Drapable Hybrid Carbon/Steel Textiles for Aircraft Lightning Strike Protection", 2024. (In prep)

Goals of Architecting Textile Composites

Improve the performance of textile composites and optimize them to enable damage-tolerant and durable structures

Current State-of-the-Art

Standard (set) weave patterns

Hybridization mostly limited to using different fabric layers

The benefits of weave architectures is underutilized

Architected weaving for enhancing fracture energy

- Tewani, Cyvas, Perez, Prabhakar, Arxi-Textile composites: Role of weave architecture on mode-I fracture energy in woven composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Volume 188, 2025.

ML frameworks to predict pattern ↔ property

- Feng, P Subramaniyan, Tewani, And Prabhakar, “Physics-Constrained Neural Network for Design and Feature-based Optimization of Weave Architectures”, *Composites Part A*, 2024.

Hybrid carbon/metal composites for lightning strike protection

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Outline

I. Architected weaving for enhancing fracture energy *

II. ML frameworks to predict pattern ↔ property

III. Hybrid carbon/metal composites for lightning strike protection

* Tewani, Cyvas, Perez, Prabhakar, Arxi-Textile composites: Role of weave architecture on mode-I fracture energy in woven composites, ***Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing***, Volume 188, 2025.

I. Architected weaving for enhancing fracture energy

Key Research Questions:

- Can we introduce varying patterns to guide crack propagation (potentially tortuous) in woven composites?
- What is the influence on fracture energy?

ARCHITECTED WOVEN COMPOSITES

In this study, we explore avenues of incorporating variable weave patterns that influence in-plane fracture energy.

Plain Weave

Twill Weave

4H Satin Weave

Type 1

Type 2

Type 3

Fracture tests

Uniform weave composites exhibited nearly consistent G_{IC} with crack propagation spread over a narrow value range

Transition regions between different sub-patterns in architected weave composites exhibited a sudden increase in G_{IC} , while remaining nearly consistent within sub-patterns. Thereby, introducing crack path tortuosity.

Weave architecture characterization

- Uniform Patterns

- Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM): characterizes the texture by considering the spatial relationship of pixels, that is, by calculating homogeneous and non-homogeneous transitions in different directions.

$contrast = b + c \implies$ Inhomogeneity,

$correlation = \frac{d - \mu_x \mu_y}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$

$IH = \frac{b + c}{a + b + c + d}$

$energy = a^2 + b^2 + c^2 + d^2$

$homogeneity = a + \frac{b}{2} + \frac{c}{2} + d$

Geometrical Parameters

Crimp factor is not considered

Same transition factor (δ)

n_g /I.H. maps

Crimp factor into account

Transition factor (δ) =

$$\left(\frac{n_g}{IH}\right)_{High} - \left(\frac{n_g}{IH}\right)_{Low}$$

Area factor (ρ) =

$$\frac{\text{Area of lower } n_g}{\text{Area of surrounding higher } n_g}$$

Skewness factor (σ) =

$$\frac{\text{Long length of shape in lower } n_g}{\text{Shorter length of shape in lower } n_g}$$

Summary

Moderate jumps

Type - I

High jumps

Type - II

Lower jumps

Type - III

Weave pattern	Transition factor (δ)	Area factor (ρ)	Skewness factor (σ)	Minimum / Maximum $G_{Ic}(KJ/m^2)$	Average $G_{Ic}(KJ/m^2)$
Type - I	7.23	0.96	1	22.52 / 149.277	74.87 \pm . 34.85
Type - II	10.5	0.54	1	19.90 / 157.957	69.23 \pm . 40.79
Type - III	10.5	0.24	2.67	22.33 / 137.155	55.78 \pm . 30.97

We want:

- High Transition Factor δ
- High Area Factor ρ
- Low Skewness Factor σ

Summary

- **Fracture energy, G_{IC}**
 - Uniform weave composites exhibit nearly consistent fracture energy values with crack propagation.
 - The findings show that different uniform weave architectures result in different failure mechanisms that can be tuned to suit the design requirements.
- **Counter-intuitive R-curves for architected weave composites**
 - We showed, for the first time, that G_{IC} values increased at the transition regions from one sub-pattern to another.
- **Proposed three geometrical factors for architected weaves**
 - To characterize their effects on the fracture energy of woven composites. Higher transition (δ) and area (ρ) factors and lower skewness factor (σ) are favorable to promote change in failure mechanisms when a crack propagates from one sub-pattern to another, resulting in higher fracture energy.

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I. Architected weaving for enhancing fracture energy

II. ML frameworks to predict pattern \leftrightarrow property *

III. Hybrid carbon/metal composites for lightning strike protection

* Feng, P Subramaniyan, Tewani, Prabhakar, Physics-Constrained Neural Network for design and feature-based optimization of weave architectures, ***Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing***, Volume 187, 2024.

II. ML frameworks to predict pattern ↔ property

Research Questions

- **Key research questions related to 2D woven composites we seek to answers are:**
 - How can we build a bi-directional bridge between woven composite architecture and its mechanical properties?
 - How to optimize the woven composite's mechanical properties using 'physically meaningful' features?

Weave Pattern & Material Machine Learning Representation

- We consider a 6-by-6 woven pattern - $2^{6 \times 6}$ different patterns and $2 \times n^6$ different material sequences, where n is the number of materials to choose from.

- Weave material for bi-material model is represented by a binary vector.
- For single material woven model, the material vector is uniform constant. '0' in Material Vector means Material 1 and '1' means Material 2.

Woven Fabric Composites - FEA Setup

9000 Sample Each

Single Material Woven
Bi-Material Woven

Many-To-One Mapping!

Overview of Woven Composite Machine Learning Approach

Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) for FDP

(Pat + Mat \Rightarrow Mod)

Overview of Woven Composite Machine Learning Approach

Physics-Constraint Neural Network (PCNN) for BDPa

(Mod + Mat \Rightarrow Pat)

+

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Prediction Accuracy

Neural Network performance is evaluated based on mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), with 9000 samples:

A_t is the actual value, F_t is the predicted value, and n is the total sample size

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{A_t - F_t}{A_t} \right|$$

FDP Prediction: (Mat+Pat→Mod)

Error Rate	E_1	E_2	G_{12}
Single-Material Woven	1.86%	1.89%	0.25%
Bi-Material Woven	4.08%	3.76%	1.84%

BDPb Prediction: (Mod+Pat→Mat)

Error Rate	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	Prediction Time
Woven-Decoder	11.74%	11.73%	11.50%	«1sec
Woven-GAN	15.28%	12.35%	26.99%	«1sec
PCNN	5.53%	5.65%	4.10%	«1sec

BDPa Prediction: (Mod+Mat→Pat)

Error Rate	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	Prediction Time
Woven-Decoder	7.87%	7.26%	0.33%	«1sec
Woven-GAN	4.34%	5.27%	0.31%	«1sec
Woven-GA	0.05%	0.01%	0.58%	60 mins 18 secs
PCNN	2.38%	1.72%	0.31%	«1sec

Error Rate	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	Prediction Time
Woven-Decoder	9.31%	9.45%	5.01%	«1sec
Woven-GAN	10.83%	11.71%	10.62%	«1sec
PCNN	3.60%	3.71%	1.34%	«1sec

Bi-material woven

Single material woven
Bi-material woven

Weave Architecture Representation using GLCM

- Binary weave pattern gives us 4 of 2-by-2 GLCM, which are 16 GLCM features in total
- Haralick GLCM features uniquely represent key features in original physical space, making GLCM features useful for optimizing woven patterns
- To understand what features contribute to woven composite's improved overall modulus, we performed a regression analysis to predict the modulus directly from the target statistical features.
 - We observe that contrast and correlation are negatively correlated with the woven composite's overall modulus, while energy and homogeneity are positively correlated.

Table 10: Sign of weights for weave pattern features

	Contrast	Correlation	Energy	Homogeneity	Contrast	Correlation	Energy	Homogeneity
	GLCM 1				GLCM 2			
Single Material	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
Bi-Material	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
	GLCM 3				GLCM 4			
Single Material	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
Bi-Material	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+

Summary

- We developed ML frameworks to bridge weave architectures and corresponding in-plane moduli
- We proposed Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) to characterize non-uniform weave patterns for optimization. We have shown that the GLCM features effectively capture the weave architecture in the physical space
- Combining ML with feature-based optimization strategy, we can determine optimal woven composite designs.

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III. Lightning Strike Protection for Polymer Composites

- Composites are extensively used in aerospace industries.
- Compared to metal counterparts, composites are more resistive. Hence, *more susceptible* to lightning strike damage.
- Need for lightning strike protection (LSP) on the aircraft exterior to provide a continuous conductive path.

Goal: Elucidate role of intrawoven lightning strike protection (LSP) on lightning dissipation and damage under electric arc impact.

Key Research Questions?

- Can we hybridize carbon fiber textile to create an intralaminar LSP to minimize damage?
- What effect does introducing conductive yarns have on the resistivity of composites?
- Can we introduce patterns to effectively dissipate the current with minimum damage?

INTRAWOVEN LIGHTNING PROTECTION SYSTEM

In this study, we explore avenues to develop hybrid weaves to effectively dissipate lightning strike.

Background – metallic LSP

Expanded metal foil and mesh LSP in Airbus 350 exposed due to paint flaw

Rehbein et al., *Compos Part A-Appl. S.* (2017)

Guo et al., *Compos Part A-Appl. S.* (2019)

Drापability and Electrical Resistivity

Electrical Resistivities

Material	Fabric	Composite thickness (mm)	Electrical resistivity ($\Omega.cm$)
<i>Carbon/Carbon (Reference)</i>	C/C	1.40	0.56 ± 0.08
<i>Carbon/stainless steel</i>	C/SS	1.16	0.15 ± 0.02
<i>Carbon/stainless steel (reduced)</i>	C/C-SS	1.19	0.18 ± 0.05

Nomenclature

*0 direction corresponds to the direction of 3K carbon fiber in the weave.

Material	Number of C/C fabric	Number of hybrid fabric	Thickness (mm)	Density (g/cm^3)	Nomenclature
<i>Carbon/Carbon (Reference)</i>	6	0	1.60	1.27	C/C
<i>Carbon/stainless steel</i>	5	1	2.203	1.64	C/SS1L
<i>Carbon/stainless steel</i>	4	2 [0/90]*	2.75	1.83	C/SS2L
<i>Carbon/stainless steel (reduced)</i>	5	1	2.267	1.41	C/C-SS1L
<i>Carbon/stainless steel (reduced)</i>	4	2 [0/90]*	2.843	1.47	C/C-SS2L

Lightning strike tests

Current: 40 kA Waveform A

Mass loss

C/C
2.981%

C/SS-1L
0.070%

C/SS-2L
0.038%

Impact Surface

Summary – Lightning Strike Damage

C/C vs C/SS1L and C/SS2L

C/C vs C/C-SS1L and C/C-SS2L

Residual Properties

Summary

- Hybrid weaves with stainless steel yarns enhance current dissipation and reduce Joule heating during electrical impacts.
- C/C composites lost >90% of flexural properties after strike.
- Hybrid weaves limited the drop in flexural properties to as low as ~9%
- Fabric form can allow high drapability for complex geometries and easy integration into industrial prepreg processes.
- Metal fiber ratio and weave patterns can be tuned to optimize LSP, weight, and mechanical performance.

Big Questions

- 1. How can we effectively characterize and further optimize weave architectures accounting for multiple patterns, materials, and their tow geometries?**
- 2. How to identify parameters for more localized failure and fracture of woven composites?**
- 3. What AI/ML tools can be most beneficial in this direction?**

Thanks for listening.

Questions?

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LAB'S
WEBPAGE

Research Themes

Interconnected Themes

Establish process-structure-property relationships for manufacturing and designing

Elucidate damage and failure mechanics in multi-physics environments

Fundamental Research Questions:

- How do manufacturing processes impact the internal architecture?
- Can we tailor the effective properties by combining mechanics-based designs and controlling process induced internal architecture?
- How does internal architecture influence global behavior (thermo, chemo, mechanical, etc.) in multi-physics conditions?

“Architected composites rely on the concept of exploiting internal architecture, which is a combination of hierarchical patterns/morphologies, solid distribution and base material properties to achieve effective material properties unattainable by traditional composites/monolithic solids.”

Weave Pattern Representation using GLCM

- **GLCM, Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrices, is a statistical method of examining texture that considers the spatial relationship of pixels.**
- **We use Haralick texture features, which consists of four statistical features: contrast, correlation, energy, and homogeneity.**

- GLCM's Contrast and Homogeneity tell the frequency of in-homogeneous ($0 \rightarrow 1, 1 \rightarrow 0$) and homogeneous ($0 \rightarrow 0, 1 \rightarrow 1$) transitions
- GLCM's Energy tells the ratio of pattern transitions in physical space.

Manufacturing Constraints

We propose to find weave patterns by modifying the target modulus within specific ranges, which we call as Modulus Bound Relaxation:

$$M_{new} = M_{old} + R \times B$$

M_{new} = updated new modulus vector and M_{old} = target modulus vector containing E1, E2, G12

$R \in [-1, 1]^{d=3}$ is a 3-by-1 vector, with each element randomly generated between -1 and 1.

B is a range of scaling factor of R , the upper and lower bound of B can be specified by the user.

$R \times B$ determines the maximum relaxation we want for the target modulus vector.

- Target modulus = [32,32,28] (Nearly Extreme Case for E1 and E2)
- Here we can find a woven composite without continuous yarn or fiber, by sacrificing modulus within a certain range

New Modulus = [30.89, 30.73, 28.88]

- Modified solution obtained in 30sec

Tensile tests

Internal Damage Assessment

Residual Properties

Material	Lightning Strike		
	Surface Temperature ($^{\circ}C$) (max. after 60 seconds)	Damage Area (mm^2) Impact side	Back side
<i>C/C</i>	88.2	6207.33	6162.48
<i>C/SS1L</i>	63.2	2490.66	3441.93
<i>C/SS2L</i>	57.8	1013.18	2884.96
<i>C/C-SS1L</i>	71.7	3095.79	3957.91
<i>C/C-SS2L</i>	60.0	2064.87	3608.44

Internal Damage Assessment: Micro-CT Scan

